

Training objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation: A Sri Lankan study

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Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V.M. (2006). Training objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation: A Sri Lankan study. The International Journal of Training and Development, 10(3), 227-247

This Version is available at: [10.1111/j.1468-2419.2006.00256.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2419.2006.00256.x)

ABSTRACT

Using a stratified random sample, this paper examines training practices of setting objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation in Sri Lanka. The paper further set out to compare those practices across local, foreign and joint venture companies based on the assumption that there may be significant differences across companies of different ownership. The findings revealed evidence of the awareness and practice of setting objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation. Overall the results of ANOVA did not confirmed the hypotheses that foreign owned companies would exhibit more training practices of objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation than that of local and joint venture companies. The paper addresses existing practice and implications.

INTRODUCTION

Training is a process of updating the knowledge, developing skills, bringing attitudinal and behavioural changes, and improving the ability of the trainee to perform his/her tasks efficiently and effectively (Palo and Padhi, 2003). There is an important role for a more formalised and structured approach to training. Training is enhanced only if those are structured and planned through meaningful assessment mechanisms. Only by so doing, training could be designed in such a way that it is a valuable experience for the trainee and fulfil the training requirements to operate and co-operate effectively in an organisational context. The purpose of this study was to examine the training practices of setting objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation in the Sri Lankan context.

In the Sri Lankan context, it is an accepted fact that human resource has and will continue to play a significant role in the global competition. With the advent of the open economy in the country in 1977, the enhancement of organisational effectiveness has become a matter of vital importance in meeting complex demands of the new business environment. The Sri Lankan literature suggests that changes occurred from 1977 has made a significant impact on the realisation of the importance of training as a major aspect in the organisational process (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2000; Chandratilake, 1997). On one hand, Sri Lankan government has been taking steps to enhance industry relevant employee skills to attract foreign investment. On the other hand, local entrepreneurs have recognised that the availability of high quality employees, in fact, places organisations at a competitive advantage over others even within the same industry and inadequacy of expertise as a major constraint, have taken concrete measures to organise training programmes in their organisations (Dept. of National Planning, 1992).

As the importance of training continues, important as it is to the future of the discipline and the HRD profession is to address whether training practices are echoed in the developing countries like Sri Lanka. This is important as the credibility of management idea is partly determined by its diffusion across the world. Also, such credibility will be enhanced if the idea is viewed to be applicable in various contexts. However, irrespective of encouraging signs of growing investment on and incidents of training, training practices remains dubious due to lack of empirical studies in the Asian developing country context, specifically, none of such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka where business operations have been increasing and have a high profile. Within this context the study focuses on training practices of setting

objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation of company specific off-the-job training programmes provided by companies themselves and through local training agencies to employees in supervisor grades (lower level managers) to middle management grades in Sri Lanka. The study further investigates the potential differences of the above practices across foreign, joint venture and local companies operating in Sri Lanka. It is hypothesised that foreign companies will exhibit more training practices of the above than that of local companies and joint venture companies. The conclusions address the existing practice and implications.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Setting objectives for training is the process of translating the needs identified into terms of observable and measurable behaviour. Specific and unambiguous objectives state the changes expected in terms of organisational and individual performance, which could be used to design training programmes (Scholl and Brownell, 1983; Wills, 1998). The objectives should describe behaviour (what the trainee will be expected to do) and conditions (under which the behaviour has to occur) which can be measured both inside and outside the training environment and standards (the acceptable level of performance) (Wills, 1998). In most occasions training is concentrated more at the individual level than at the organisational level. Smith and Hayton (1999) provide evidence that in Australia the role of the individual emerged as an important factor in the training decision-making. The lack of use of organisational criteria to set training objectives may be due to the difficulty of evaluation- training is only one of the many factors that influence performance of an organisation (ILO, 1986).

Based on the management axiom - 'nothing will improve until it is measured' (Mathis and Jackson, 1994) - the training programmes have to be assessed in terms of the programme itself, behaviour outside the training environment, and whether it has had the desired effect (Wills, 1998). In other words, training has to be assessed in terms of training transfer, validation and evaluation. Training transfer ensures that the training has transferred into the work environment. Effective training can be gauged by the capacity of trainees to apply knowledge, skills and abilities gained in training to their work environment and maintained over time in their job contexts- a sustainable transfer (Pidd, 2004). The post training environment plays an important role in determining the degree to which the training gained is transferred to the workplace (Kirby et al, 2003, Kontoghiorghes, 2004; Pidd, 2004; Seyler et al, 1998). The research evidence reveals that organizations face problems in training transfer. One of the main reasons that hinder training transfer is work environment is not supportive in the use of new skills acquired by the participant. These influence the actual usage of skills at workplace and ease of transfer. Though Clarke (2002), van der Klink et al (2001) and Tracy et al (1995) found evidence for the influence of supervisor and co-worker support on training transfer as mixed, Seyler et al (1998) and Kontoghiorghes (2004) found that work environment was associated with differences in participants' motivation to learn the skills during training and to transfer. Training programmes of Australia and New Zealand were under pressure to increase their programmes' practical relevance and delivery of immediately applicable skills (Avery et al 1999). Sri Lankan organisations too face problems in the transfer of skills from training programmes to work places (Sivanesan 2000; Wijetunge 1992; Weliwita 1991). Especially, in the instances where training programmes were provided through local training agencies as such agencies did not involve in

follow-up and monitoring activities to help staff to transfer their skills to workplace (Sivanesan 2000; Wijetunge 1992). This as an important issue, which emphasizes the need of the involvement of HRD professionals in the post-training situations.

Validation ensures that the training programme meets, and continues to meet, the objectives that have been set for it - whether the participants have reached the required standard- and should reflect the perceptions of the participants and reveal perhaps unintended effects of the training (Mumford, 1997; Wills, 1998). Validation is critical as training cannot be transferred to the work environment unless it has met its objectives. Good validation system not only shows what needs to be changed but also prevent changing a training programme for change's sake (Wills, 1998). When drawing a line between where validation ends and evaluation begins, according to Wills (1998) validation is "a systematic analysis of data and judgmental information, collected during a training programme, which is designed to ascertain whether the programme achieved its specified aims and objectives" (p191). Validation can be done from two perspectives - validation against participants' perceptions and comments, and validation against the programme objectives (Wills, 1998). Participants' perceptions and comments could be obtained using end-of-programme feedback sheets. Smith and Hayton (1999) and Manning and Poljeva (1999) noted that the most common method of validation is obtaining feedback. Despite the weakness of halo effect, participants' feedback is essential, as their feedback is one of the main factors that determine a programme's credibility and reputation and that identify unexpected effects of the training (Wills, 1998). When validation information provides significant negative symptoms, organizations take actions, such as revising training programmes (Wills, 1998). In the Sri Lankan context, there was no indication whether training programme contents were being revised time to

time to keep up with emerging needs (Wijetunge 1992). The Sri Lankan literature reveals the possibility of providing compulsory training programmes through external training institutions without assessing the actual training needs. According to Gunatilaka (1987), the reason for the continuation of compulsory training programmes without any assessment might be the value of obtaining qualifications in getting promotions. If so, such programmes may be continued even though the needs have not been properly assessed and the programme ceased to be relevant. However, validation does not provide information on whether the gained skills and knowledge contribute anything towards business effectiveness. Neither does it tell whether the objectives were the right ones. It is evaluation that deals with these (Wills, 1998).

Evaluation determines the effect of training at individual, departmental and organisational levels (Wills, 1998). Though several approaches could be used to evaluate training, there is no one best way of evaluation, just as there is no one best way to train. One of the ways of evaluating training is assessing effectiveness. Wills (1998) categorised the training effectiveness measures into four- financial, utilisation, time, and process. When evaluating training effectiveness Mole (2000) stressed the importance of having criteria from the point of selection and design of the training programmes; this corresponds with the concepts behind process approach. The process approach to evaluate training effectiveness is goal-oriented. Typically, each component in the process provides ongoing evaluation feedback to other components in order to improve the overall system; it allows establishing checkpoints to keep under control and produce the required outputs. These checkpoints could be established at the beginning, during and at the end of the training. The checkpoints at the beginning answer the question of whether the correct outputs will be produced. The checkpoints during the process answer the question of whether the correct

outputs are being produced. The checkpoints at the end answer the question of whether the correct outputs have been produced. Therefore, the process approach could be considered as a helpful mean of preventing or solving training problems. However, Avery et al (1999) revealed the lack of statistical data available on the overall effectiveness of training in Australia and New Zealand. Khatri (2000) in the context of Singapore, too, found that organizations neglect training evaluation. However, evaluation is not required after each and every training programme; validation is normally sufficient to get the required information (Wills, 1998).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study specifically addresses the following research questions.

1. Do companies set training objectives and if so, what are the criteria used to set objectives and how they are utilized?
2. Do companies make inquiries into training transfer and if so, what prevents training transfer?
3. Do companies validate training programmes and if so, what are the methods used for validation?
4. Do companies evaluate training programmes and if so, at which levels evaluation takes place?
5. Do companies evaluate training effectiveness and if so, to what extent organisations are satisfied with the outcomes?

6. By addressing above specific research questions the study further sought to find out: are there any significant differences across foreign, joint venture and local companies in the practices of setting training objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation?

The main focus of the study is to investigate the above mentioned dimensions of training. When broadly construed, learning at work encompasses formal training, informal training, embedded learning, and innovation (Stern et al, 2004). Some studies found informal on the job training as a dominant skill acquisition strategy for the majority of workers in many economically developing countries (Barber, 2004). However, here only formal off the job employer sponsored training is examined. Further, though it might be interesting to look for differences in ratings between HR managers and trainees (participants) as there could be differences in their perceptions of training and training events, the study is not designed in such a way to probe the same dimension from the two sets of sample units. A detailed description of the methodology used is given in the section on Methods.

METHOD

Population and sample selection

The need of generalizing training practices led to select one particular industrial sector of the country- export-oriented apparel manufacturing and to select a sample based on stratified random sample method.

From late 1970s export-oriented apparel manufacturing industry was expanded rapidly and today it has emerged to the position of the country's main export earner and the largest single employment provider in the industrial sector. Hence, policy makers have placed heavy emphasis on this industry as means of promoting employment and generating foreign exchange earnings by recognising it as the main contributor to the overall economic development (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2000). Though investment by East Asian and European manufacturers fuelled the growth of the Sri Lankan export-oriented apparel manufacturing industry, at present, apart from the wholly local owned companies (local), several companies have been set up in the industry as wholly foreign owned companies (foreign) or as foreign and local joint venture companies (joint venture) (BOI).

The export-oriented apparel manufacturing companies registered under Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) served as the population of the study. BOI is the primary government authority responsible for identifying, promoting and facilitating both foreign and local investments in Sri Lanka (BOI). It is compulsory by law that all foreign investments (wholly foreign owned and foreign/local joint venture) should come into the country through BOI (BOI). Therefore, this provides easy and systematic access to foreign invested companies. At the time of the study there were 207 companies (82 Local, 68 Foreign, 57 Joint venture) registered under BOI, operating in Free Trade Zones of the country.

It was decided to select a proportionate stratified random sample of 100 companies (40 Local, 33 Foreign, 27 Joint venture) for the study. Simple random sampling method was used in drawing the desired number of elements from each subcategory (local, foreign, joint venture). However,

due to various reasons the total number of companies that agreed to participate in the study amounted to 78 (32 local, 26 foreign, 20 joint venture). The number of companies in each category of the sample (local, foreign, joint venture) consisted of more than 35 per cent of the companies in the each category of the population. Of the companies that had responded to the study, 59 per cent of the companies have employed more than 10 managers and 26 per cent of the companies have employed 6 to 10 managers. With regard to the number of total employment in the companies, 46 per cent of the companies have employed 101 to 500 employees, 33 per cent of the companies have employed 501 to 1000 employees, and 18 per cent of the companies have employed more than 1000 employees. All the 78 companies have separate HR departments/units. 51 per cent of the companies have separate HRD units/departments.

In the study, two different perspectives of the training were probed using two sets of samples- HR managers and participants of training (trainees) - as there are disadvantages of collecting survey data from one source (Ichniowski et al, 1996; Nichols, 1986). From the 78 companies that agreed to participate in the survey, all 78 HR managers responded to the questionnaire (32 local, 26 foreign, 20 joint venture). In selecting a sample of participants of training, initial contacts were made with 4 employees in supervisor grades (lower level management) to middle management grades who were not working in the same managerial function in the 78 companies (4x78), using simple random sample method. The total number of responses obtained amounted to 219 (104 local, 65 foreign, 50 joint venture). 18 HR managers (7 local, 6 foreign, 5 joint venture) and 25 participants (10 local, 8 foreign, 7 joint venture) from the stratified simple random sample willingly agreed to participate in the interviews. Information on the demographics of the samples is shown in table 1.

INSERT TABLE 1 ABOUT HERE

Instrument

The data was collected through survey questionnaires and interviews in order to capture the dimensions of the investigation. It is anticipated that the results of the questionnaire survey may provide access to breadth of experience while the interviews may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Two questionnaires targeting HR managers and participants were constructed. The preliminary investigations gave insight into the aspects studied in the industry. To collect necessary information in a manner that puts the least burden on expected respondents, information that could be accessible from other sources, such as interviews was excluded from the self-administered questionnaires. Questions in the self-administered questionnaires took the form of closed ended questions in a five-point Likert-scale as they have proven themselves to be more efficient and ultimately more reliable. When exploring methods used for validation, what prevents training transfer, etc., questionnaire listed a range of options and a tick box labelled “other” was added to the list to enable respondents to state any other that exist in connection to the items in his/her company, which was not offered by the questionnaire. The survey questionnaire targeting HR managers covered following main aspects.

- Existence of setting training objectives, criteria used to set objectives and how they are utilized

- Existence of making inquiries into training transfer and what prevents training transfer
- Reasons that prevent training transfer
- Existence of validation of training programmes and methods used for validation
- Existence of evaluation of training programmes and levels at which evaluation takes place
- Existence of evaluating training effectiveness and whether companies are satisfied with training effectiveness.

The survey questionnaire targeting participants covered:

- Immediate superior managers' support in transferring training
- Human resource managers' support in transferring training
- Ease of transferring training to work place.
- Actual usage of training gained at work place.
- Relevance of training programmes to their present job
- Relevance of training programmes to their career development
- The confidence on ability to use the skills
- Satisfaction regarding duration of the programmes
- Satisfaction regarding time received to practice the skills during the programmes

The both questionnaires were pilot-tested to improve the reliability and face validity of the instruments. For the pilot survey eight HR managers and twelve participants from the local, foreign and joint venture companies participated. The fieldwork was carried out from mid 2002 to mid 2003. As mentioned in sample selection, all 78 HR managers from the 78 companies of

the stratified random sample (32 local, 26 foreign, 20 joint venture) that agreed to participate in the survey responded to the questionnaire; 219 participants from the stratified random sample (104 local, 65 foreign, 50 joint venture) responded to the questionnaire.

Interviews were deemed necessary to complement the survey questionnaires to corroborate the information that had been gathered from the survey questionnaires and to elaborate the field by exploring a greater variety of experiences offered by participants and HR managers. It was decided to conduct interviews after the preliminary analysis of data obtained from questionnaires for two reasons. First, the answers to the survey questionnaires may provide some new insights, which should be further investigated. Second, if the researcher had found out something, which should have been asked but omitted in the questionnaires, then during the interviews those areas can be dealt with. The interviews were structured along the main outline topics that were covered in the questionnaires but with open questions to explore those in more detail. As mentioned in sample selection, 18 HR managers (7 local, 6 foreign, 5 joint venture) and 25 participants (10 local, 8 foreign, 7 joint venture) from the stratified random sample willingly agreed to participate in the interviews.

Data analysis

Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS programme. In addition to descriptive statistics, one way between-subjects analysis of variance (ANOVA) or chi-square test was used appropriately to explore the impact of ownership form. HR managers' and participants' comments were categorised and incorporated into the discussion of the survey results.

RESULTS

Training objectives

Table 2 presents means and standard deviations for the extent to which companies set training objectives. It is apparent that the companies frequently set training objectives than otherwise ($\bar{X} = 3.28$). As shown in table 2, there are no significant differences across companies of different ownership on this aspect. Table 2 also presents criteria used in setting training objectives. Most popular criteria used to set objectives were to improve skills/abilities ($\bar{X} = 4.40$), to improve knowledge/understanding ($\bar{X} = 4.23$) and to improve attitudes ($\bar{X} = 4.24$). The least used criteria was to complete a project ($\bar{X} = 3.00$). It is evident that setting objectives based on individual criteria is the most favoured - skills ($\bar{X} = 4.40$), attitudes ($\bar{X} = 4.24$) and knowledge ($\bar{X} = 4.23$). Among organisational criteria, setting objectives in terms of achieving business plans is the most favoured ($\bar{X} = 3.96$). However, overall it is ranked 5th. Setting objectives based on profits is ranked 8th with a mean value of 3.50. However, further analysis of ANOVA revealed that there are no significant differences across companies of different ownership in all the criteria used to set objectives, which are shown in table 2 ($p < 0.05$).

INSERT TABLE 2 ABOUT HERE

Table 3 shows the ways in which the pre-set objectives are utilised throughout the training effort. The data suggests that training objectives are frequently used to chose the type of training programmes ($\bar{x} = 3.71$), to provide an overview of what participants are going to learn ($\bar{x} = 3.48$), to explain resource parsons what is expected after the completion of the programme ($\bar{x} = 3.23$) and to validate/evaluate training programmes ($\bar{x} = 3.21$). The objectives are least utilised to develop company specific training programmes ($\bar{x} = 3.16$). As shown in table 3, ANOVA reveals that there are significant differences across companies in the utilisation of training objectives to develop company specific training programmes. Further analysis of LSD shows that joint venture companies are more likely to use training objectives to develop company specific training programmes than that of their counterparts in the local companies. But there are no significant differences between foreign and joint venture companies. This suggests that local companies prefer to use pre-set off-the-job external programmes than developing their own company specific programmes.

INSERT TABLE 3 ABOUT HERE

Training transfer

Table 4 presents means and standard deviations for the extent to which companies make inquiries into training transfer. It is apparent that the companies make inquiries into training transfer ($\bar{x} = 3.34$). As shown in table 4, there are no significant differences across companies of different ownership.

INSERT TABLE 4 ABOUT HERE

Table 4 also reveals that participants are satisfied with the ease of transferring the learned skills/abilities to the work place ($\bar{x} = 3.46$) and satisfied with the use of newly acquired skills/abilities at work ($\bar{x} = 3.34$). During the interviews participants revealed that programmes they have received are relevant to their jobs and use the acquired capabilities to fulfil daily business engagements. When it is about technical aspects, all most all the things learned can be applied. Participants are also satisfied with the help they have received from their immediate superiors in the transfer ($\bar{x} = 3.41$). During the interviews participants revealed that companies encourage those who has completed the training programmes to share what is learnt during the programmes with other colleagues of the department. This method of sharing is beneficial as it flows in the knowledge gained by the individual to the work organisation. If other members of the organisation are also aware of the benefits of grasping such knowledge, the organisation as well as the individuals can benefit from such knowledge flows. As shown in table 4, ANOVA indicates that the impact of ownership is not significant in 3 out of 4 items presented in the table. However, there are significant differences in the participants' satisfaction with the help they received from HR managers in the transfer. Further analysis of LSD showed that participants from foreign companies are more satisfied with this aspect than that of the participants from local companies. But there are no significant differences between foreign and joint venture companies.

Reasons that prevent training transfer

Table 5 shows the reasons which prevail in companies that prevent training transfer. The data reveals that the most frequently identified reason that prevents training transfer is little control over transfer process ($\bar{x} = 3.14$). The reason that ranked 2nd is work environment is not supportive in the use of new skills learnt ($\bar{x} = 3.09$). The reason that ranked 3rd is difference between work environment and training environment ($\bar{x} = 3.04$). During the interviews participants revealed that in the instances where training programmes were provided through external training institutions, such institutions did not involve in follow-up and monitoring to help the participants to transfer skills to the workplace. Table 5 also displays the mean values by ownership and their ANOVA values. The results of ANOVA indicate that the impact of ownership is significant in non-supportive work environment, difference between work environment and training environment and inferior training programmes. Further analysis of LSD reveals that in local companies non-supportive work environment is frequent than that of in joint venture companies. In foreign companies, difference between work environment and training environment is more than that of in both joint venture companies and local companies. In foreign companies, the design of inferior training programmes is frequent than that of in both joint venture companies and local companies.

INSERT TABLE 5 ABOUT HERE

Training validation

Data relating to validation of training programmes is shown in table 6. The data reveals that the companies validate training programmes ($\bar{X}=3.23$). As shown in table 6, ANOVA reveals that there are no significant differences across companies ($p < 0.05$).

INSERT TABLE 6 ABOUT HERE

Table 6 also presents data in relation to methods used for validation. The training programmes are validated against participants' perceptions and comments and against the programmes objectives. The most popular source of validation against perceptions and comments is obtaining feedback from participants ($\bar{X} = 3.71$). Participants' responses reveal that the training programmes they have had undergone are relevant to their present jobs ($\bar{X} = 3.57$) and relevant to their career development ($\bar{X} = 3.71$). Furthermore, participants are confident with their ability to use the skills at the workplace ($\bar{X} = 3.99$). However, participants are less satisfied with the duration of the training ($\bar{X} = 3.07$). The second popular source of validation against perceptions and comments is obtaining feedback from participants' immediate superiors ($\bar{X} = 3.58$). Data suggests that validating against resource persons' comments is not very popular ($\bar{X} = 2.83$). During the interviews, HR managers revealed that they obtain feedback from the participants using standard end-of-training feedback sheets that comprise a questionnaire and a comments section. These feedback sheets are designed in such a way to obtain information on to what extent participants are satisfied with the programme, whether they think the programme meet its

objectives and what they think of resource persons. The comments section provides them an opportunity to give their own comments. This type of feedback is obtained from participants just after completing a training programme. After about three months of completing a programme, feedback is also obtained from participants' immediate superiors. All the immediate superiors are requested to provide their feedback using a separate feedback sheet. As Manning and Poljeva (1999) revealed getting necessary insight is not always easy from employees and employees are not used to express their feelings toward authority figures. To overcome this situation some companies obtain comments of participants by requesting them to submit a report after the completion of training. In the report participants are requested to write what they have learnt during the programme, how those can be applied within the company and resources if any needed.

Responses to the validation against training programmes shows that companies revise training programmes to incorporate required changes ($X = 3.36$). Those required changes are identified from the feedback obtained from participants, participants' immediate superiors and resource persons. However, further analysis of ANOVA revealed that the impact of ownership is not significant in all the aspects shown in table 6 ($p < 0.05$).

Training evaluation

The table 7 shows the data relating to training evaluation. The data suggests that training evaluation is not very popular ($X = 2.84$). However, further analysis of ANOVA revealed that there are no significant differences across companies in terms of ownership types. During the

interviews, few HR managers revealed that they give tests for participants after the completion of the training. It is also revealed that participants' immediate superiors observe whether they apply the newly acquired skills on work. Overall, it can be identified that these companies use Kirkpatrick's model to evaluate training. Companies evaluate training at the reaction level by feedback sheets, at the learning level by giving tests, at the behaviour level by observing how they apply the skills, and at the results level by comparing participants' present and past performance criteria, such as quality indices, labour turnover, production rates, and reduction in complaints.

The companies evaluate training at 3 levels. According to table 7, the companies are satisfied with the improvements in the participants ($\bar{X} = 3.46$), improvements in participants' departments ($\bar{X} = 3.38$) and improvements in the companies after the completion of training ($\bar{X} = 3.22$). However, the results of ANOVA revealed that there are no significant differences across the companies of different ownership in the satisfaction with the items shown in table 7 ($p < 0.05$).

INSERT TABLE 7 ABOUT HERE

Training effectiveness

Table 8 shows data in relation to training effectiveness. According to table 8, evaluating training effectiveness is not very frequent ($\bar{X} = 2.92$). Further, the companies are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with the training effectiveness results. However, the results of ANOVA revealed that

there are no significant differences across companies on all the aspects shown in table 8 ($p < 0.05$).

INSERT TABLE 8 ABOUT HERE

Preliminary investigations revealed that companies frequently use process approach in evaluating effectiveness. Some of the most common process measures used are shown in table 9. According to table 9, training needs come from immediate bosses who like their subordinates to be trained ($\bar{x} = 3.24$) and as compulsory training requirements ($\bar{x} = 3.07$). However, during the interviews it was revealed that the compulsory training programmes were conducted in the manner in which they were originally designed or provided through external training institutions without assessing the compulsory training needs time-to-time. Intended participants also request training ($\bar{x} = 2.94$). The companies prioritise training demand ($\bar{x} = 3.29$). During the interviews HR managers revealed that after receiving training requests they discuss the outcomes of training needs analysis with other affected parties within a company, such as heads of the departments prior to prepare training plans. Most frequently companies have to prioritise the training needs based on criteria such as the urgency of the need, budgetary restrictions, and time availability or departments' ability to release all personnel who requested a particular training programme at one time. The companies introduce new training programmes to link training to business plans ($\bar{x} = 3.52$). The companies prepare training plans for each financial year ($\bar{x} = 3.64$). HR managers revealed that managing Director's or the Board of Directors' approval was obtained for training plans before implementation. However, most of the training plans are prepared for a period of one year, which shows that the training effort is perceived as a short-term activity. The

companies prepare annual training budgets ($\bar{x} = 3.58$). HR managers revealed that the companies run their training/HRD units as cost centres and get the approval of the Managing Director or the Board of Directors for annual training budgets. Only few HR managers revealed that the total budget available for training depends on overall performance of the company; total budget for the training vary from one year to another. However, none of the companies have predetermined amount as a training budget, for instance, a certain percentage of the turnover, etc. However, as one HR manager stated cash may not be the best measure. The prevention of intended participants from undergoing training because of other company engagements obtained a mean value of 2.72. The companies get the confirmation of completion of the training ($\bar{x} = 3.71$) and amend the training records ($\bar{x} = 3.64$). HR managers revealed that the companies maintain training records containing information such as required training for the current post, already completed training programmes, scheduled dates, and training costs. The records are maintained in terms of the level of management or function within the organisation, such as production. Maintaining separate training records is a requirement under international quality standards (ISO). The impact of international quality standards in maintaining training records was also observed by Smith and Hayton (1999) in their study. However, only a limited number of companies maintain computerised training records.

INSERT TABLE 9 ABOUT HERE

DISCUSSION

Using a stratified random sample of 78 export-oriented apparel manufacturing companies operating in free trade zones, the study sought to examine training practices of setting objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation in the Sri Lankan context. Management activities have increasingly been globalizing (Ishizaka, 1996). Though attention has been devoted to international comparisons, less attention has been paid to Asian developing countries (Bartlett et al, 2002; Cunningham et al, 1996; Taylor, 2001). Specifically, none of such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka, where international business operations have been increasing and have a high profile. Within this context, the study further set out to compare training objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation across foreign, joint venture and local companies based on the assumption that there may be significant differences across companies of different ownership. Overall, the study revealed evidence of the awareness and practice of setting objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation.

To summarise, training begins with the specific and clear objectives that affect the contents to follow. However, the data revealed less use of objectives to develop company specific training programmes. This situation could also lead at times to compromise the objectives by the necessity of offering already existing training programmes. Having said that companies should provide and encourage training, those have to be aligned with business needs. Training effort was considered more as a means of improving specific job related skills- training is concentrated more at the individual level than at the organisational level. However, this situation is not only prevailing in Sri Lanka. Smith and Hayton (1999) also provide evidence. However, the study

revealed that companies introduce new training programmes and revise the contents to keep up with emerging trends and to align with business needs. In reality, resources are limited and training priorities had been decided.

The companies look into training transfer and this is consistent with previous Sri Lankan studies (Sivanesan, 2000; Weliwita, 1991; Wijetunge, 1992). The companies face problems in training transfer. Though it is obvious that to foster training transfer and confidence to perform, participants must be able to practice within realistic job conditions (Kontoghiorghes, 2004), this study revealed that the participants were not satisfied with the time received to practice the skills during the training. Sometimes the most important element of training transfer has little to do with the training programme itself. The data reveals that the most frequently identified reason that prevents transfer is lack of control over transfer process- the transition from training environment to work place is not managed properly. Seyler et al (1998) and Kontoghiorghes (2004) found that work environment was associated with differences in participants' motivation to learn the skills during training and to transfer. However, in this study, motivation of participants had not scored higher values to be considered as a main reason that prevent training transfer. Skills that are not learnt during the training could be connected to both insufficient time for participants to gain confidence in using the skills taught and workplace environment constraints that prohibit implementing training (Clarke, 2002). In this study though skills not learnt ranked 5th in preventing training transfer, the participants were less satisfied with the duration of training. However, as mentioned earlier, non supportive work environment was recognised as one of the main reasons. Therefore, though this study did not examine the relations between reasons that prevent training transfer in the Sri Lankan context, based on the findings it

is safe to conclude that all these could be closely interrelated. The study revealed that when training was provided through external training institutions, such institutions did not involve in follow-up and monitoring to help participants to transfer skills to workplace. This is consistent with findings of Sivanesan (2000) and Wijetunge (1992). This emphasises the need of HR managers' and immediate bosses' involvement in the post-training environment reviewing participants performance on a continuous basis.

The training programmes were validated from two perspectives- validation against participants' perceptions and comments, and validation against the programme objectives. The formal use of feedback at three levels was evident- at the level of participants, at the level of participants' immediate superiors and at the level of resource persons. Participants revealed that the training they had received was relevant to their jobs and used the acquired skills/abilities to fulfil daily business engagements. Therefore, it is possible to argue that even though training has a short-term focus, it can still offer to improve or enable participants' to learn skills, knowledge and abilities that are needed to perform his/her present job. Participants' perceptions and comments were obtained using end-of-training feedback sheets. The data revealed the possibility of compulsory training programmes being conducted in the manner in which they were originally designed or provided through external training institutions without assessing the compulsory training needs time-to-time.

The companies evaluate training programmes starting from the individual level and then proceeding to the other two levels, departmental and organisational. However, it is revealed that companies were mostly satisfied with the results at the individual level. Overall, it is evident that

validation and evaluation are regarded as necessary aspects of training effort; there is a considerable awareness and practice of training validation and evaluation within the apparel manufacturing industry. International standards require all the companies to provide training for all employees and also to have a proper system to validate and evaluate those. Export-oriented apparel manufacturers identify international standards of certification as a source of competitive advantage, especially, to compete with recently entered countries to the industry. In many cases, the first step organisations take towards developing formal training programmes is to abide by ISO 9000 standards, which have resulted in a growing awareness about and led to more universal training practices. However, the results of the analysis revealed that companies were more likely to validate training than evaluate them, showing that companies eager to ensure that training meets and continue to meet its stated objectives than to ensure that it has had the desired effect-practical usefulness of training. However, this situation is not only prevailing in Sri Lanka; Avery et al (1999) and Khatri (2000) also provide evidence. The results for the existence of training plans were not consistent with the studies of Sivanesan (2000) and Wijetunge (1992). However, the maximum duration of planning was one year. Therefore, as Handy (1987) observed, there is no preference to the long-term perspective in training in the Sri Lankan sample. The study also revealed the difficulties in getting release for training from normal organisational duties and often the number of participants who attended training was lesser than that had been called for the training. These reflect lack of concern for the training effort by superiors.

IMPLICATIONS

The framework of the study is based on investigating whether there are differences across companies of different ownership- foreign, local, and joint venture- in the training practices of setting objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation. Overall the results of ANOVA did not confirm the hypotheses that foreign owned companies would exhibit more training practices of setting training objectives, transfer, validation and evaluation than that of local and joint venture companies. To sum up, ANOVA results suggested that local companies are not alien to prevalent practices; they are also practising them to some extent. This situation does not contradict with the thought that foreign companies do bring their ideas and joint venture companies could provide a supportive environment in which both partners could create an effective organisational environment. The findings seem to reveal that local companies are not detached from the rest of the world. Local companies' familiarity to these practices could be attributed to several reasons. First, it could be explained in the specific historical context. Hofstede (1993) argued that the concept of HRD would never have been invented in Asia; it came as a foreign idea, to be adapted to different local situations. It is a fact that for 400 years British rule left its mark on the system of administration, industry and commerce and even after the colonial period, locals had to follow the footsteps of running business using these experiences (Wijewardena and Wimalairi, 1996). As the study of Lawler et al (1995) reveals in the context of India and Thailand, the British colonial system had enormous influence on management practices of Sri Lanka. Further, most of the training programmes offered and the textbooks used by the Sri Lankan educational institutions were based on the techniques and concepts developed in the US and Europe; most of the foreign experts who were involved in numerous bilateral and multilateral technical assistance

programmes have also encouraged rapid technological and educational advancement primarily via skills and knowledge transfer (Chinniah, 1986; Nanayakkara, 1992). All these could lead local entrepreneurs to be more aware of the prevalent systems.

Second, local companies' familiarity to practices could be explained in the specific industry context. The global competitive environment in the export-oriented apparel manufacturing seems to play far more significant role in policy choices. In this context, while companies are competing in the world markets they have to adapt the dominant patterns in those markets. Management concepts enter into the play in the forms of the requirements of foreign buyers and international standards (ISO). This situation agrees with Kerr et al (1960), Chen (1995) and Bartlett et al (2002) who argued that industrialisation could ensure that management practices become increasingly uniform. In this regard, local companies have to modernise its management practices by grafting prevalent practices of the industry. By so doing, local companies could be more competitive in the world apparel market. It should not be forgotten that all export-oriented apparel manufacturers manufacture the products for the global market, which is mainly the US and the EU. Further, by so doing, local companies could be more competitive in the local labour market in attracting high-flyers. International businesses operate in the export-oriented apparel manufacturing industry as foreign owned companies and as joint ventures for more than 25 years; local companies are in competition with them to attract newly passed out graduates and experienced workers from the labour market. Thus, foreign and joint venture companies could eventually work as the agents of modifying local management practices. Similar findings were revealed in Bartlett et al's (2002) study.

However, the concepts of HRM and HRD might be both country specific. Hence the findings of the study do not close the door for further investigations on the aspects based on more qualitative case studies of comparative analysis to test the underlying basic assumptions of where those are different.

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TABLES

Table 1: Sample composition

HR managers (%)			
<u>Years of service in the present company</u>		<u>Highest educational qualification</u>	
5 years or less	41	Postgraduate degree	9
6 to 10 years	47	Degree or equivalent	36
More than 10 years	12	Diploma	55
<u>Age</u>		<u>With professional qualification</u>	
31 to 40 years	28	Yes	64
41 to 50 years	56	No	36
More than 50 years	15	<u>Gender</u>	
		Male	81
		Female	19
Participants of training (%)			
<u>Years of service in the present company</u>		<u>Age</u>	
5 years or less	77	30 years or below	53
6 to 10 years	20	31 to 40 years	36
More than 10 years	3	41 to 50 years	8
		More than 50 years	3
<u>Number of training opportunities received</u>		<u>Highest educational qualification</u>	
More than 10 times	9.1	Post graduate degree	3
8 to 10 times	5.0	Degree or equivalent	40
5 to 7 times	21.0	Diploma	25
Less than 4 times	58.0	GCE A/L	31
Never had an opportunity	6.8	GCE O/L	1
<u>When last received training</u>		<u>With professional qualification</u>	
Currently receiving	26.3	Yes	76
Less than 1 year ago	40.2	No	24
1 year to 2 years ago	20.6	<u>Gender</u>	
More than 2 years ago	12.9	Male	78
		Female	22

Table 2: Training objectives

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)
Set training objectives	3.28 (.92)	3.31 (1.11)	3.15 (.88)	3.40 (.59)
Criteria used to set objectives				
Improve skills/abilities	4.40 (.74)	4.41 (.66)	4.38 (.80)	4.40 (.82)
Improve knowledge/understanding	4.23 (.75)	4.16 (.84)	4.23 (.71)	4.35 (.67)
Improve attitudes	4.24 (.84)	4.22 (.70)	4.19 (1.02)	4.35 (.81)
Apply learning in work environment	4.01 (1.12)	3.81 (1.40)	4.15 (.92)	4.15 (.81)
Increase participants' reputation at work	3.21 (1.12)	3.00 (1.13)	3.58 (.94)	3.05 (1.23)
Complete a project	3.00 (1.31)	2.59 (1.31)	3.01 (1.12)	3.25 (1.44)
Increase profits	3.50 (1.28)	3.43 (1.36)	3.92 (1.05)	3.05 (1.31)
Increase flexibility	3.56 (1.03)	3.34 (1.09)	3.76 (1.03)	3.65 (.93)
Increase participants' commitment	3.94 (.92)	4.00 (.84)	3.96 (.99)	3.85 (.98)
Achieve business plans	3.96 (.99)	4.06 (.84)	4.03 (.87)	3.70 (1.34)

Table 3: Utilisation of objectives throughout the training effort

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
To chose training programmes	3.71 (1.01)	3.53 (1.24)	3.76 (.77)	3.95 (.82)	1.09	.340
To develop company specific training programmes	3.16 (1.08)	2.81 (1.27)	3.15 (.88)	3.70 (.80)	4.46	.015
To validate/evaluate training programmes	3.21 (.96)	3.03 (1.04)	3.19 (.89)	3.50 (.88)	1.45	.241
To provide an overview of what participants are going to learn	3.48 (1.19)	3.64 (1.33)	3.07 (1.09)	3.75 (1.01)	2.35	.102
To explain resource parsons what is expected after the completion of the programme	3.23 (1.23)	3.09 (1.44)	3.11 (1.07)	3.60 (1.04)	1.19	.308

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 4: Training transfer

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Make inquiries into training transfer	3.34 (1.13)	3.28 (1.25)	3.69 (.97)	3.0 (1.07)	2.25	.112
Participants' views						
Ease of transfer	3.46 (.94)	3.44 (.94)	3.49 (.94)	3.44 (.95)	.06	.940
Actual usage of skills at workplace	3.34 (.93)	3.35 (.92)	3.34 (.98)	3.32 (.88)	.02	.981
Help participants' receive from the immediate superior	3.41 (1.01)	3.49 (0.96)	3.28 (1.01)	3.42 (1.10)	.82	.439
Help participants' receive from HR managers	2.83 (1.25)	2.46 (1.29)	3.31 (1.25)	2.80 (1.00)	3.43	.038

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 5: Reasons that prevent training transfer

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Poor training needs identification	2.79 (1.15)	2.91 (1.20)	3.04 (1.07)	2.30 (1.08)	2.67	.076
Non-supportive work environment	3.09 (10.91)	3.28 (.95)	3.23 (.71)	2.60 (.94)	4.20	.019
Little control over transfer process	3.14 (.87)	3.16 (.93)	3.36 (.81)	2.85 (.81)	1.94	.150
Skills are not learnt during the training	2.88 (.90)	2.77 (.88)	3.00 (.93)	2.90 (.91)	.44	.645
Difference between work and training environment	3.04 (.86)	2.90 (.83)	3.50 (.70)	2.65 (.87)	7.06	.002
Lack of motivation of participants	2.89 (.97)	2.93 (.89)	3.00 (1.19)	2.70 (.80)	.56	.570
Inferior training programmes	2.68 (1.07)	2.16 (1.06)	3.30 (.88)	2.70 (.92)	9.83	.000

Note: $p < 0.05$

Table 6: Training validation and methods used for validation

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)
Validate training	3.23 (.97)	3.22 (1.18)	3.00 (.84)	3.55 (.68)
Methods used for validation				
1. Validation against perceptions and comments				
1.1. Participants' perceptions and comments	3.71 (1.08)	3.65 (1.28)	3.50 (.98)	4.05 (.75)
Relevance of training for the present job	3.57 (1.00)	3.60 (1.03)	3.49 (1.01)	3.63 (.94)
Relevance of training for the career development	3.71 (1.00)	3.74 (1.02)	3.68 (1.05)	3.68 (.91)
The confidence in ability to use the skills	3.99 (.77)	4.05 (.77)	3.97 (.73)	3.91 (.82)
Satisfaction regarding duration of the training	3.07 (1.03)	3.03 (1.03)	3.03 (1.01)	3.21 (1.08)
Satisfaction regarding time received to practice the skills during the training	3.16 (.91)	3.10 (.93)	3.23 (.87)	3.19 (.92)
1.2. Participants' immediate superiors' perceptions and comments	3.58 (1.02)	3.68 (1.11)	3.38 (1.09)	3.65 (.74)
1.3. Resource persons' perceptions and comments	2.83 (1.27)	2.68 (1.33)	2.76 (1.09)	3.15 (1.38)
2. Validation against training programmes				
Revise training programmes	3.36 (1.13)	3.18 (1.33)	3.23 (1.06)	3.80 (0.76)
Cancel training programmes	2.73 (1.07)	2.78 (1.18)	2.88 (.86)	2.45 (1.14)

Table 7: Training evaluation and the levels of evaluation

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)
Evaluation of training	2.84 (1.05)	2.77 (1.23)	2.76 (.90)	3.05 (.94)
Evaluation levels				
At individual level	3.46 (.84)	3.40 (1.01)	3.57 (.75)	3.40 (.68)
At department/section level	3.38 (.84)	3.40 (.79)	3.46 (.98)	3.25 (.71)
At company level	3.22 (.80)	3.20 (.84)	3.26 (.87)	3.20 (.69)

Table 8: Training effectiveness

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)
Evaluate effectiveness	2.92 (.89)	2.81 (1.02)	2.88 (.90)	3.15 (.58)
Satisfied with effectiveness	3.10 (.75)	2.91 (.77)	3.36 (.75)	3.10 (.64)

Table 9: Process measures used in evaluating training effectiveness

Item	Overall Mean (SD)	Local Mean (SD)	Foreign Mean (SD)	Joint venture Mean (SD)	ANOVA	
					F	Sig.
Immediate boss requests training	3.24 (1.08)	3.16 (1.09)	3.29 (1.26)	3.30 (.86)	.13	.874
Intended participants request training	2.94 (.97)	2.81 (1.02)	3.12 (1.01)	2.90 (.85)	.70	.497
Compulsory training needs	3.07 (1.26)	3.09 (1.28)	3.29 (1.33)	2.72 (1.06)	3.00	.052
Prioritise training demand	3.29 (.94)	3.13 (1.12)	3.58 (.70)	3.20 (.83)	1.82	.168
Introduce new training programmes	3.52 (.99)	3.38 (1.21)	3.48 (.91)	3.80 (.61)	1.15	.320
Prepare training plans	3.64 (1.11)	3.50 (1.29)	3.46 (1.06)	4.10 (.78)	2.36	.101
Prepare training budgets	3.58 (1.14)	3.43 (1.24)	3.26 (1.11)	4.25 (.71)	5.12	.008
Prevented from undertaking training	2.72 (1.22)	2.82 (1.26)	2.57 (1.22)	2.72 (1.16)	.81	.443
Get confirmation of completion of training	3.71 (1.11)	3.83 (1.27)	3.38 (1.06)	3.95 (.82)	1.83	0.168
Amend training records	3.64 (1.16)	3.66 (1.23)	3.44 (1.08)	3.85 (1.18)	.68	0.507

Note: $p < 0.05$